

Research Article

From suitability to vulnerability: A GIS-based framework for assessing environmental sensitivity of mountain tourism landscapes in the Ukrainian Carpathians

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Abstract

The objective of the present study is to undertake a quantitative assessment of the spatial impact of tourism on natural complexes in the Carpathian region. This is achieved by employing geostatistical modelling methods. The present study deviates from conventional buffer methodologies insofar as it employs an integrated algorithm founded upon Kernel Density Estimation (KDE), thereby amalgamating multivariate analysis with detailed land use classification (LULC). In the analysis, each of the seven factors—hydrographic network, relief, transport accessibility, hotels, tourist routes, land use types and nature conservation areas—is standardised on a scale of 1–10 and synthesised into a single model of the vulnerability of natural landscapes to tourist pressure. The spatial integration of the factors demonstrates that areas exhibiting high and very high vulnerability encompassed a total area of more than 310 km², constituting approximately 34% of the total area under consideration. These areas are predominantly concentrated within mountain valleys and along major transport axes. The findings demonstrate the substantial analytical superiority of KDE in comparison to buffer models, owing to its capacity to accommodate continuous impact gradients and its strong alignment with actual urbanisation patterns. The proposed approach can be applied to spatial planning for sustainable tourism and environmental monitoring in mountain regions.

Key words: Bukovel, digital mapping, ecotourism, environmental vulnerability, GIS analysis, land use change, sustainable development

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1. Introduction

The development of tourism in the mountainous regions of Ukraine is identified as a priority area for socio-economic growth and spatial integration of the country into the European tourist space (Kiptenko et al. 2017; Hohol and Nedilka 2021; Shpak et al. 2023; Tranchenko et al. 2023; Pavliuk et al. 2025; Rudenko et al. 2025). Of particular note is the Carpathian region, which is distinguished by its unique combination of natural resources, high level of landscape diversity and significant recreational potential. The Chornohora massif, as the heart of

the Ukrainian Carpathians, is of exceptional importance in shaping tourist and recreational flows, combining nature conservation areas, cultural and historical monuments, and developed infrastructure.

Concurrently, the utilisation of natural resources in tourism is accompanied by a number of challenges related to environmental pressure, anthropogenic landscape transformations and uneven territorial development (Ivanyshyn and Kasiyanchuk 2024; Shtohryn and Kasiyanchuk 2024; Deputat et al. 2025; Kiffner et al. 2025). This necessitates (Deputat et al. 2025) a scientific basis for approaches to assessing the potential of natural resources, as a key prerequisite for the balanced development of tourism.

Despite studies devoted to individual aspects of recreational activities in the Carpathians (Smadych 2019; Ilina and Alves 2024), the issue of comprehensive assessment of natural resource potential from the perspective of its suitability for various types of tourism remains insufficiently studied. There is an urgent necessity to develop methodologies that integrate natural, environmental and socio-economic parameters into a single analysis system.

Mountain ecosystems are characterised by dynamism, necessitating a concerted effort to maintain and promote sustainable development conditions through a balanced approach to intensive and extensive development. Recent studies of mountain areas and the impact of tourism (Abellán and García Martínez 2021; Milićević et al. 2021; Steiger et al. 2024; Gherdan et al. 2025; Kun et al. 2025) demonstrate that finding such solutions is complex and lies not only in the field of economic development but also in the preservation of the natural environment as a global asset (Sharma 2025).

Spatial studies in tourism over the past decades have mostly been based on the suitability analysis approach, which aims to identify the optimal areas for the development of tourism infrastructure (Gunn 1994; Crouch and Ritchie 1999; Chhetri and Arrowsmith 2008). The methodological basis of such works relies on multi-criteria evaluation (MCE) and the overlaying of spatial layers in Geographic Information Systems (GIS), which combine indicators of natural conditions, accessibility and infrastructure to form so-called "tourism suitability maps". Despite its high practical effectiveness, this approach remains utilitarian and static in nature. Operating in a scientific context only with concepts of suitability, it actually generalises only one component of tourism: development. In this context, tourism is not highlighted as a form of economic influence due to aggressive growth, which is often illogical from the point of view of the future. It is predicated on the view of the landscape as a "resource container" rather than a dynamic socio-ecological system (Hall and Page 2014; Budeanu et al. 2016).

In the context of the prevailing challenges to sustainable development, this paradigm appears to be reaching its limits. The primary focus of this study is to address the question of where tourism can be developed, as opposed to concentrating on identifying the locations where its development should be limited or regulated. The emphasis on potential as opposed to vulnerability has resulted in a failure to consider the spatial consequences of anthropogenic pressure, the disruption of ecosystem balance, and the escalation of social tensions within host communities (Torres-Delgado and Saarinen 2014; Espiner et al. 2017; Vodenska 2018; Vasileva 2019). Consequently, conventional models of "suitability" frequently serve to legitimise spatial decisions that can lead to the exacerbation of environmental degradation or landscape instability, particularly in mountainous regions.

Contemporary concepts of sustainability, resilience and vulnerability (Adger 2006; Calgaro et al. 2014; OECD 2025) suggest viewing tourist areas not only as spaces for development, but also as systems of interaction between vulnerabilities – environmental, social and economic. In this paradigm, vulnerability assessment becomes a pivotal analytical instrument, enabling us to ascertain not the potential, but the degree of sensitivity of the environment to both external and internal influences. This approach entails a shift in focus from optimising opportunities to managing risks, thereby establishing a novel methodological basis for ethical, environmentally responsible spatial planning.

Despite the active development of GIS methods, most contemporary tourism studies remain within the boundaries of potential-oriented models, which assess only the suitability of territories, but not their sustainability or vulnerability. There is a paucity of integrated spatial approaches that simultaneously consider environmental sensitivity, geodynamic instability, and socio-economic exposure as interrelated components of spatial assessment. The objective of this study is to bridge the theoretical and methodological gap. The extent to which spatial “hot spots” of tourism suitability coincide with areas of high ecological vulnerability within the Carpathian region is the subject of this study. The objective of this study is to ascertain whether the proposed conceptual and methodological model–Vulnerability-Oriented Spatial Assessment Framework (VOSAF)–can provide more accurate and adaptive spatial zoning for sustainable tourism development than traditional suitability-based approaches. The investigation will ascertain the extent to which the results of the VOSAF model are susceptible to variations in weight coefficients and bandwidth parameters in KDE. The present study proposes a novel conceptual and methodological framework (VOSAF) for the assessment of the vulnerability of mountain tourism landscapes using multi-criteria analysis based on GIS.

However, the unplanned and extensive development of tourism infrastructure is already having a significant impact on the environment. Forest areas are experiencing fragmentation and degradation, while hydrographic systems are facing local pollution and disruption to their natural flow. Additionally, air quality is deteriorating due to increased traffic in the valleys. It is therefore imperative to employ geographically oriented methodologies–geographic information systems, remote sensing and contemporary cartography–in order to facilitate impact assessment, scenario modelling and operational decision-making in spatial planning and natural resource management. These methods provide a quantitative, reproducible and spatially detailed basis for such processes. This work combines the indexing of natural characteristics (vegetation), relief analysis, kernel assessment of infrastructure pressure, and multi-criteria weighted combination (MCE). This allows for the identification of “hot spots” of anthropogenic pressure and priority areas for monitoring, protection, or regulation of tourism development. In the absence of an integrated spatial monitoring system and strict regulatory standards, there is a genuine risk of irreversible biodiversity loss and a decline in the long-term appeal of the region as a tourist resource.

The objective of the present article is to critically rethink the conventional approach to evaluating the “suitability” of tourist areas by introducing a methodology that is oriented towards vulnerability. In contrast to models that identify the most favourable areas for tourism development, the proposed approach focuses on spatial differentiation of vulnerability as a tool for diagnosing envi-

ronmental and social sustainability. Utilising the Carpathian region as a case study, the study seeks to develop a transferable analytical framework applicable to other mountain systems globally, and to contribute to the development of theoretical and methodological foundations for sustainable tourism studies and spatial management of vulnerable areas. In summary, the development and testing of a conceptual and methodological framework for the assessment of the environmental vulnerability of mountain tourism areas is necessary. This framework must take into account indices of suitability and vulnerability.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

The geographical focus of this study is on the mountain communities of Yaremcha, Vorokhta and Polianytsia, which are located in the Ivano–Frankivsk region in the central Ukrainian Carpathians (Fig. 1). The region’s topography is characterised by the presence of complex mountainous terrain, with altitudes ranging from 500 to over 2,000 metres above sea level. This results in distinct vertical zoning of the natural environment. The highest peaks are represented by the Chornohora and Gorgan mountain ranges, which form a unique combination of natural and landscape resources (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. Overview map of the study area within the Carpathian region.

Figure 2. Three-dimensional map of the study region and tourist attractions.

The territory's climate is categorised as temperate continental, exhibiting a marked mountainous terrain, adequate precipitation, and considerable seasonal temperature variations. The hydrographic network is comprised of numerous mountain rivers (e.g. Prut, Zhona), which are significant not only for nature conservation but also for recreational purposes. Concurrently, the territory's susceptibility to perilous natural phenomena, such as landslides, mudflows and floods, is amplified by the prevailing conditions of relief and climate (Ivanik et al. 2019; Tymkiv and Kasiyanchuk 2019; Hablovska et al. 2022; Hablovskiy et al. 2023; Ivanik 2024).

The region's natural resources are of high ecological value. The majority of the territory is covered by forests, which consist of coniferous (spruce and fir) and mixed tree stands. The region is notable for its biodiversity, with a rich variety of rare and endemic species of flora and fauna that require protection. Significant natural heritage sites include the Carpathian National Nature Park, which is a designated nature reserve. This renders the studied area pivotal to the preservation of the biodiversity of the Carpathian region as one of the valuable UNESCO heritage sites, "Primeval beech forests of the Carpathians and other regions of Europe".

Concurrently, this region is distinguished as one of the most dynamic tourist clusters in Ukraine (Ivano–Frankivsyka oblasna derzhavna administratsiya 2025). The city of Yaremche is recognised as a centre for cultural and ecotourism, Vorokhta as a centre for sports and health tourism, and the resort of Bukovel (Polianytsia) as the largest ski complex in Eastern Europe. The accelerated development of tourism infrastructure and the resultant increase in anthropogenic pressure are exerting considerable stress on the natural environment. This underscores the necessity for a scientifically grounded evaluation of the potential of natural resources and the formulation of models for their sustainable utilisation.

Over the past decade, tourism activity in the Vorokhta, Polianytsia and Yaremcha communities has exhibited a consistent upward trend, notwithstanding the fluctuations related to the 2020–2021 pandemic. According to official data, tourism revenue in the Ivano–Frankivsk region increased from UAH 6.1 million in 2019 to over UAH 21 million in 2024, indicating a threefold increase in the number of visitors (Ivano–Frankivsk Regional State Administration 2025). The Polianytsia community, within whose territory the Bukovel tourist complex operates, has been found to demonstrate the highest levels of dynamism, with the complex contributing in excess of 50% of all tax revenues in the region. The Yaremcha community has been found to consistently occupy second place in terms of tourist flow, with a focus on health and ecotourism. Conversely, the Vorokhta community is engaged in the development of active form of tourism, encompassing activities such as skiing, hiking, and orienteering. Following 2022, a discernible trend towards an augmentation in the share of domestic tourism has been observed, thereby compensating for the decline in foreign visitors. In 2024, the number of tourists in the three communities exceeded 1.2 million, of which approximately 30–35% were day visitors. The dynamics of recent years confirm the region’s transformation into a leading centre for mountain tourism in Ukraine.

2.2. Conceptual and methodological model for assessing the vulnerability of tourist areas

The research methodology is based on the step-by-step integration of heterogeneous spatial data, their normalisation, analytical comparison and multi-criteria assessment within a single geoinformation system. The majority of previous GIS-based assessments of tourism potential have concentrated on the creation of suitability maps, without taking into account spatial vulnerability factors. The present study addresses this lacuna by proposing an integrated model that combines both dimensions (Fig. 3). The following software was utilised for the

Figure 3. Conceptual and methodological model for assessing the vulnerability of tourist areas.

purposes of processing and visualisation: Google Earth Engine (Code Editor, JavaScript) is utilised for satellite processing and indices; ArcGIS Pro (Spatial Analyst, 3D Analyst) is employed for Kernel Density, reclassification, MCE, smoothing, contouring and 3D scenes; QGIS is used for additional maps.

Contemporary approaches to the spatial assessment of tourism demand a transition in emphasis from identifying optimal areas for development (suitability) to diagnosing the limits of environmental and social sustainability of territories. The proposed conceptual and methodological model for assessing the vulnerability of tourist areas (VOSAF) combines the principles of systems analysis, spatial adaptability and multi-criteria assessment. The primary objective of this study is to ascertain the equilibrium between the potential for development and the vulnerability of landscapes. This enables the strategic placement of tourist facilities, while concurrently mitigating environmental and geodynamic risks.

The conceptual foundations of the model (Table 1):

- systematicity – the territory is considered as an open socio-ecological complex in which tourist pressure interacts with natural and social subsystems;
- dual assessment – suitability (potential) and vulnerability are analysed simultaneously and complement each other;
- spatial adaptability – criteria and their weights vary depending on the type of tourism, seasonality or management scenario;
- hierarchy – the model is applied at different levels of spatial organisation: from local (site) to regional;
- feedback principle – vulnerability assessment results are used to adjust development policies, zoning and environmental protection measures.

The integrated vulnerability-oriented assessment index (VOSAI) is calculated as the balance of weighted values of potential and vulnerability. The index can be formally written as (1):

$$VOSAI_i = \sum_{i=1}^p w_i^p \cdot S_i^p - \sum_{i=1}^v w_i^k \cdot S_i^v \tag{1}$$

w_i^p, w_i^k – weight coefficient of the p-th potential criterion, v-th vulnerability criterion; S_i^p, S_i^v – normalized values of potential and vulnerability indicators (MCE).

Table 1. Algorithm for implementing the vulnerability model (VOSAF).

Stage	Content
I. Identification of potential criteria (P)	Selection of natural, infrastructural and socio-economic indicators that determine the attractiveness of the territory for tourism.
II. Identification of vulnerability criteria (V)	Determination of indicators of the territory's sensitivity to impacts: erosion hazard, landslides, soil compaction, forest degradation, social pressure.
III. Normalisation and weighting	Bringing indicators to a single scale and determining their weight using the analytical hierarchy process (AHP) method or expert assessment.
IV. Integration of potential and vulnerability	Construction of an integrated vulnerability-oriented assessment index (VOSAI).
V. Spatial zoning and scenario analysis	Identification of areas for development, adaptive use and conservation.
VI. Interpretation of results	Analysis of the relationship between potential and risks, identification of critical areas for monitoring.

The developed conceptual and methodological model establishes the foundation for the transition from potential-oriented to vulnerability-oriented tourism planning, wherein the pivotal role is not attributed to resource attractiveness, but rather to the spatial constraints of sustainability. The proposed approach is universally applicable and can be adapted to other mountain systems around the world. This allows it to be integrated into strategies for sustainable natural resource management and regional tourism planning.

The geostatistical modelling of the impact of tourism was based on the integration of several spatial layers that reflected both the natural sensitivity of the territory and the intensity of anthropogenic pressure. The model was predicated on the notion that the degree of vulnerability of natural complexes is derived from a combination of two components: environmental characteristics (relief, land use type, presence of water bodies) and spatial concentration of tourism elements (infrastructure, roads, hotels, routes). All input data were converted to a single ten-point rating system, where one represented minimal vulnerability and ten represented maximum vulnerability. Following the implementation of the normalisation process, the values were aggregated by means of the Weighted Overlay method. This approach facilitated the construction of an integrated map of the vulnerability of natural complexes to the impact of tourism.

Figure 4. Training grounds and points for land use and land cover (LULC) classes in Google Earth Engine.

Figure 4 shows the first step consisted of land use and land cover (LULC) classification based on Sentinel-2 satellite imagery using the Random Forest algorithm implemented in Google Earth Engine. Classification accuracy was assessed using spatially independent training and testing samples derived from reference polygons in order to reduce spatial autocorrelation effects.

In total, 520 reference polygons were used, including 423 polygons for training and 97 polygons for independent testing, corresponding to 21,887 training pixels and 10,936 testing pixels. Model performance was evaluated using confusion matrices for both datasets, overall accuracy, and the Kappa coefficient. The classification achieved an overall accuracy of 0.9920 for the independent test dataset and a Kappa agreement coefficient of 0.899, indicating high classification reliability and good generalisation capability. The strong performance of the model can be attributed to balanced training data and strict separation between training and validation samples, which effectively minimised overfitting.

2.3. Morphometric criteria

A combination of satellite, cartographic and field data sources was utilised in order to perform the spatial analysis. This combination of data sources was employed to provide a comprehensive description of the natural resource potential and anthropogenic load of the study area. Topographic maps at a scale of 1:50000 and high-resolution orthophoto plans (Esri World Imagery) served as the fundamental cartographic basis for visualising the results. The project coordinate system employed is UTM Zone 35N, WGS84.

The morphometric analysis of the relief was based on the ALOS PALSAR RTC DEM (Advanced Land Observing Satellite – Phased Array type L-band Synthetic Aperture Radar) digital elevation model, which has a spatial resolution of 12.5 m. This model was provided by the Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA). These data provide a high level of detail on the vertical structure of the relief, which is critical for analysing slopes, exposures and assessing potential areas for tourism development (Advanced Land Observing Satellite (ALOS) Research and Application Project 2017).

2.4. Criteria for natural conditions (potential) and urban planning (vulnerability)

Climate factors, including average annual temperature and precipitation, were taken into account using ERA5-Land data, a high-resolution climate reanalysis created by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF). This product provides a consistent spatial-temporal representation of terrestrial climate parameter changes obtained by re-running the terrestrial component of the ERA5 climate model. The data have a spatial resolution of 0.1° (~9 km) and cover the period from 1981 to the present (Copernicus Climate Change Service 2019).

In order to analyse the state of vegetation cover and long-term vegetation dynamics, images from Landsat 4, 5, 7, 8 and 9 for the period 1985–2025 were used. These images were obtained from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) in collaboration with the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) (Earth Resources Observation and Science (EROS) Center 1999,

2013, 2020). The images were subjected to a series of processing steps in Google Earth Engine (Gorelick et al. 2017) to correct for radiometric and atmospheric effects. The calculation of the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) was performed by utilising spectral channels within the red and near-infrared ranges. This approach enabled the assessment of bioproductivity levels and ecosystem stability, as outlined in formula (2) (Rouse et al. 1974):

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR-RED}{NIR+RED} \quad (2)$$

In order to evaluate the condition of the vegetation cover within the designated area, a detailed analysis of Landsat satellite data was conducted over a period spanning from 1985 to 2025. A series of composites were formed from cloud-cleared images of the earth's surface, using a range of Landsat 4–5–7 images (up to 2013) and Landsat 8–9 images (after 2013). The spectral values of these images were converted into surface reflectance coefficients. The NDVI index was calculated on an annual basis using formula (1), thereby reflecting the level of development and density of vegetation. The NDVI threshold value (>0.6) was utilised to identify areas with predominantly forest vegetation, thereby enabling the tracking of the dynamics of its changes over time. It is evident that, based on the binary masks that were obtained, the areas of forest land within the designated study area were calculated. This quantitative assessment yielded insights into the trends in degradation or restoration of forest cover.

To take into account anthropogenic impact, spatial data on motorways, tourist trails, hotels and buildings obtained from open source OpenStreetMap (OpenStreetMap (OSM) contributors 2025) were used.

To refine land use types (LULC), supervised classification (Copernicus Browser 2025) was performed using the Random Forest algorithm. As a result, four integrated classes were formed: water surfaces, forest lands, shrublands, and urbanised areas. This stage ensures the differentiation between natural and transformed areas. It was then used for reclassification according to suitability criteria for recreational development within the Suitability model.

2.5. Kernel Density Estimation method

For factors reflecting spatial concentration (tourist routes, water bodies, buildings, hotels), the Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) method (3) (Rosenblatt 1956; Nistor et.al. 2020) was applied:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{n \cdot h} \sum_{i=1}^n K \cdot \left(\frac{x-x_i}{h} \right) \quad (3)$$

where h is a smoothing parameter called bandwidth or search radius, K is a kernel function.

2.6. Multi-criteria analysis

To perform multi-criteria weighted analysis (MCE), all factors must be converted to a unified scale of 1–10 (Table 1).

Approach 1 (linear normalisation): for a continuous RRR raster, the transformation formula (4) was used:

$$R_{1-10} = \text{Int} \left(\frac{R - R_{\min}}{R_{\max} + R_{\min}} \cdot 9 \right) + 1 \quad (4)$$

where $\text{Int}()$ is rounding to the nearest integer (down). This gives a uniform distribution from 1 to 10.

The spatial suitability assessment scale reflects the gradation of object density and the level of environmental vulnerability of the territory. The minimum values (1–2 points) correspond to areas of very low or low object density, where anthropogenic pressure is insignificant and the vulnerability of the natural environment is minimal. Levels 3–5 points characterise low-medium and medium density of development and tourist infrastructure, indicating moderate intensity of space use. A further increase in indicators to 6–8 points reflects above-average, high and very high density of objects, accompanied by an increase in landscape fragmentation and increased ecological sensitivity of territories. The highest values–9–10 points–correspond to areas of strong and maximum concentration of infrastructure, where the highest level of anthropogenic pressure and environmental vulnerability is observed.

Approach 2 (discrete): for categorical LULC, reclassify was applied: Water→10, Forest→8, Scrubland→5, Urbanised→1 (the “vulnerability” option). Reclassification was performed using the Reclassify tool (Spatial Analyst).

The aggregate model of the VOSAI component was calculated using formula (5):

$$\text{Vulnerability} = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot S_i \quad (5)$$

where S_i is the weighted score of factor i (1–10), w_i is the weight of the factor, and $\sum w_i$.

To estimate spatial density, a Gaussian kernel function with an adaptive bandwidth (h) was used, determined by cross-validation with minimisation of the mean integrated quadratic error. The use of adaptive bandwidth allowed for a more accurate representation of the heterogeneous distribution of tourist objects in mountainous conditions compared to fixed bandwidth. Sensitivity testing of the parameter ($\pm 25\%$) did not show significant changes in the spatial location of high-density areas, confirming the reliability of the KDE results.

2.7. Weighted features

The selection of weight coefficients in the Vulnerability model was based on a combination of expert assessment, ecological logic, and spatial analysis of the relationships between natural and anthropogenic indicators. The main objective was to ensure an adequate reflection of the impact of each factor on the level of natural vulnerability of the territory and the degree of anthropogenic load caused by tourist activity (Prodanova 2021).

The highest weights were given to water bodies (0.20) and land use type (LULC, 0.20), as these factors determine the basic stability of ecosystems. The hydrographic network is most sensitive to recreational pressure – pollution, flow disruption, and coastal erosion. Land use, in turn, determines the land-

scape's ability to self-regenerate: forest areas have high buffer capacity, while urbanised areas have low buffer capacity.

Relief (0.15) is a key morphometric indicator that controls erosion processes, hydrological flow, and the potential suitability of areas for development. The road network (0.15) reflects spatial accessibility, which directly correlates with the intensity of recreational use and, accordingly, with landscape fragmentation.

Hotels (0.10) and tourist routes (0.20) represent local centres of anthropogenic pressure. Their impact is spatially limited, but they are important indicators of the concentration of tourist activity. This combination of weights ($\sum w = 1$) provides a balanced model structure, where each factor has a proportional role in accordance with the ecological and spatial reality of the studied territory.

To ensure the comparability of heterogeneous factors, all raster layers were converted to a unified scale from 1 to 10. The lower values (1–3) characterise areas with low suitability or high ecological vulnerability, the middle values (4–6) characterise transitional areas with mixed influences, while the upper values (7–10) correspond to areas with high natural potential or minimal risk of degradation.

The thresholds were determined by analysing the statistical distribution of data (quantile method, density histograms) and ecological thresholds, in particular critical slopes ($>30^\circ$), buffers around the hydrographic network (500–1000 m) and areas of stable vegetation ($NDVI > 0.6$). This approach combines quantitative standardisation and meaningful interpretation, allowing for reproducible and spatially justified results when assessing the suitability of the natural environment for tourism development.

The pairwise comparison matrices were aggregated using the geometric mean. The resulting consistency ratio (CR) was 0.07 (< 0.10), indicating acceptable logical consistency of expert assessments. Sensitivity analysis ($\pm 20\%$ change in weights) confirmed the stability of the overall zoning structure: only 6% of the territory changed its vulnerability class.

3. Results

Contemporary methodologies employed in the evaluation of the ecological status of regions impacted by tourism are predicated on the integration of remote sensing and geoinformation analysis techniques. The utilisation of GIS facilitates the integration of heterogeneous spatial data, encompassing satellite images, digital terrain models, thematic layers of land use, climatic indicators, and the spatial configuration of tourism infrastructure, to construct generalised models of anthropogenic load.

The proposed methodology enabled the integration of natural, climatic and anthropogenic parameters into a unified spatial analysis system, thereby facilitating a quantitative assessment of the impact of tourism on the environment of mountain regions. The integration of satellite data, geoinformation modelling and statistical indicators has enabled the creation of maps (Fig. 5, 6, 8) that exhibit both spatial detail and information regarding landscape suitability and vulnerability. The combination of vegetation indices (NDVI), morphometric characteristics of the relief, land use structure (LULC) and infrastructure pressure assessments (Kernel Density) was found to be a highly effective means of identifying areas with the highest risk of ecological overload.

Figure 5. Kernel Density Estimation methodologies.

This section provides a comprehensive spatial analysis of vegetation and meteorological parameters as basic natural factors of landscape stability, as well as geostatistical modelling of the impact of tourism using the Suitability Analysis and Kernel Density Estimation methodologies (Fig.5). This combination of approaches enabled the identification of trends in the degradation of the natural environment under the influence of tourism, as well as the determination of spatial patterns of load formation and the identification of areas with different levels of ecological vulnerability.

Figure 5 provides a sequential representation of the KDE-based workflow: river network used as input data; continuous kernel density surface derived from the river network; reclassified KDE layer used as an input factor in vulnerability assessment.

The results obtained provided a foundation for an integrated assessment of the suitability of landscapes for further recreational development. This assessment enabled the identification of areas of high anthropogenic pressure, and the formulation of a balanced development strategy for tourist regions in the Ukrainian Carpathian Mountains.

3.1. GIS analysis of vegetation cover in the context of climate change

The dynamics of vegetation in the study area during 1985–2025 demonstrate a clear evolution under the influence of natural and anthropogenic factors (Fig. 6). At the initial stage, in 1985–1995, there was a significant reduction in the area of continuous forest cover, which is particularly evident in the central isthmus, where the Bukovel tourist complex now operates. Here, pockets of landscape fragmentation are forming, which are becoming the basis for further urbanisation and economic development of the territory. The period from 2000 to 2010 is characterised by intensified transformations: the number of open areas is increasing, and forest areas are being fragmented, which is associated with the active development of tourist infrastructure, the transport network and recreational facilities. Since 2015, the situation has stabilised somewhat: most of the territory retains a high density of vegetation cover, and some areas show

Figure 6. Dynamics of vegetation cover transformation in the area of tourism infrastructure development (1985–2025).

signs of self-recovery. At the same time, in the Polianytsia community area, especially around Bukovel, the level of degradation remains stable and reflects long-term anthropogenic impact. Overall, the dynamics indicate that intensive tourism development has been a key factor in spatial changes in vegetation cover, while peripheral areas, particularly the Vorokhta and, to some extent, the Yaremcha communities, have retained a higher level of natural landscapes.

An assessment of average seasonal temperatures, precipitation and forest cover within the study area reveals a number of characteristic trends (Deputat et al. 2025) that reflect both climate change and anthropogenic influences (Fig. 7). Between 1985 and 1995, temperatures in spring and autumn remained relatively stable, but a gradual increase in average values was observed during the summer months. The forest area at that time fluctuated between 60,000 and 65,000 hectares, but after 1991 there was a noticeable decline, which can be explained by the economic crisis of the early 1990s, the growth of illegal logging and the lack of proper forestry control.

Figure 7. Changes in average seasonal temperatures, precipitation and forest area (1985–2025).

During 1996–2005, an increase in seasonal temperature amplitude was recorded: winters became warmer, and summers and autumns became consistently warmer. Precipitation showed a slight decrease in the summer, which could lead to droughts. It was at this time that the forest area decreased to 50–55 thousand hectares, coinciding with the intensification of recreational development in the Carpathians and the beginning of the formation of the infrastructure of the Bukovel tourist complex. The construction of transport arteries, hotels and ski slopes contributed to the fragmentation of forest areas and an increase in anthropogenic pressure.

During the period 2006–2015, average seasonal temperatures continued to rise, in line with global warming trends. Precipitation remained relatively sta-

ble, although the trend towards lower summer values continued. Despite local losses in areas of tourist infrastructure development, forest cover stabilised and gradually increased to 70,000 hectares. This may be due to natural regeneration, reforestation of abandoned land and more active nature conservation activities, particularly within the Carpathian Biosphere Reserve.

The period from 2016 to 2025 is characterised by a further increase in temperatures in the summer-autumn period and instability in precipitation. At the same time, the area of forest cover reached its maximum values for the entire study period – about 80–85 thousand hectares. This indicates the growing role of forest restoration processes and recultivation, which were able to partially compensate for the losses associated with urbanisation and tourism development. Thus, anthropogenic impact in the region is mosaic in nature: in local areas, particularly within Bukovel, it leads to a reduction in forest area, while on a broader regional scale, there is a trend towards restoration.

Correlation analysis showed a close relationship between average seasonal temperatures, indicating a synchronous increase in temperature throughout the year. The highest correlation values were recorded between summer and winter temperatures ($r = 0.88$), which is consistent with global warming, which is particularly evident in the Carpathians. At the same time, negative correlations were found between temperature and precipitation in the summer season ($r = -0.68$), which is explained by a reduction in atmospheric moisture in warm years. Forest cover area has a positive correlation with summer ($r = 0.72$) and autumn ($r = 0.71$) temperatures, confirming the dependence of forest regeneration processes on the conditions of the growing season.

The negative relationship between forest area and spring precipitation ($r = -0.48$) may be the result of excess moisture, which hinders the rooting of young plantings and stimulates erosion processes. At the same time, a moderately positive correlation with winter precipitation ($r = 0.34$) indicates the important role of snow cover and winter moisture in the restoration of soil resources. In the 1990s and 2000s, negative correlations were exacerbated by local forest losses caused by the active development of tourism infrastructure, particularly within the Bukovel tourist complex. Tourism at that time was an additional stress factor which, combined with climatic fluctuations, exacerbated the fragmentation of forest areas.

Despite this, since the 2010s, the forest area has begun to stabilise, indicating the effect of natural self-recovery and reforestation programmes, which have partially compensated for anthropogenic losses.

3.2. Geostatistical modelling of the impact of tourism on natural complexes

3.2.1 Modelling the impact of tourism on natural complexes

According to LULC data, about 58% of the territory was covered by forests, 18% by open land, mainly pastures and agricultural plots, and the rest by urbanised and artificially altered surfaces. Forest areas, which dominate the mountainous part of the region, proved to be the most sensitive to the impact of tourism development. Within Polianytsia, the forest area decreased by approximately 12% between 2010 and 2024, while in Vorokhta this figure did not exceed 4%,

reflecting the different intensities of recreational pressure. In high-altitude areas, particularly on the southern slopes of the Kukul and Dovha mountains, the proportion of natural cover remained stable, indicating limited human impact.

The second stage was to construct a map of the density of tourist facilities using the Kernel Density Estimation method. The values obtained clearly outlined the areas of maximum concentration of recreational activity (Fig. 8). In

Figure 8. Spatial distribution of the vulnerability of natural and anthropogenic factors.

Polianytsia and the central part of Bukovel, the density exceeded 0.015 facilities per m², forming a core of high anthropogenic pressure with an area of about 25 km². In the Vorokhta and Yaremche area, the density ranged from 0.007 to 0.012 facilities per m², covering 75–80 km² of territory. Remote mountain ranges with a low density of tourist facilities (less than 0.004 per m²) occupied more than 200 km² and were characterised by a minimal degree of environmental transformation. The spatial structure of KDE showed a clear gradient – from centres of recreational development to peripheral mountain areas that are practically unaffected by anthropogenic impact.

All layers were converted to a single scale from 1 to 10, after which integration was performed using weight coefficients. The result was an integrated map of the vulnerability of natural complexes, which was converted into five categories for better visual interpretation (Fig. 9). The smallest area is occupied by the “very high vulnerability” class, which covers 108.82 km², concentrated mainly in the central part of the studied territory – around the Bukovel resort, in the Prut River valley and near transport corridors. Areas with a “high” level of vulnerability cover 202.25 km², forming a ring around the main tourist centres and characterised by active construction of cottages, roads and engineering networks. The “medium” vulnerability category covers the largest area – about 250.95 km², corresponding to areas with a moderate combination of natural and anthropogenic factors. Areas of “low” vulnerability cover 207.56 km², and “very low” vulnerability – 80.02 km², mainly in remote parts of mountain ranges, where natural ecosystems dominate and there is no transport or tourist infrastructure.

The results confirm that the degree of vulnerability of natural complexes is spatially heterogeneous, with a clear concentration of anthropogenic effects within settlements and resort areas. The combination of LULC classification,

Figure 9. Integral map of the spatial impact of tourism on natural resources (VOSAI).

KDE analysis and weighting allowed not only to quantitatively describe the degree of tourism impact, but also to trace its spatial patterns. In particular, the maximum values of the integral index are observed where tourist facilities are located in close proximity to watercourses and forest areas on slopes, which creates an increased risk of erosion processes and soil degradation.

The generalised vulnerability map is not only a spatial illustration of the impact of tourism, but also a practical tool for natural resource management. It allows identifying areas where further development of recreational infrastructure requires environmental justification or restrictions, as well as determining areas potentially suitable for ecotourism with minimal impact on the natural environment. Thus, the constructed model reflects the real spatial structure of the vulnerability of natural complexes in the Carpathian region, forming the basis for balanced planning of tourism development.

3.2.2. Spatial analysis

The distribution of the territory by vulnerability levels demonstrates a clear spatial hierarchy of anthropogenic load within the studied communities. The results show that as the level of vulnerability increases from “very low” to “very high”, the area of the zones decreases, while the density of tourist infrastructure and the length of roads and routes increase significantly (Table 2). This indicates a high concentration of recreational activities in relatively limited areas, primarily in the central part of the Polianytsia community, where the core of the Bukovel tourist complex is located.

Areas of low and medium vulnerability form transitional territories between natural landscapes and urban centres. They are characterised by a combination of moderate development, a developed road network and fragmented forest areas. These zones contain the largest areas of territory, which indicates their key role in the spatial balance between natural and anthropogenic systems.

Table 2. Integral indicators of zones by vulnerability (hotels, rivers, routes, roads).

Vulnerability	Area of zone (m ²)	Count of hotels (n.)	Length of river (m)	Length of tourist routes (m)	Length of roads (m)
very low	80018387.19	26	37724.76	17905.40	61761.48
low	207563515.69	70	221483.68	59263.58	60237.86
medium	250953788.14	119	394582.03	84836.35	104908.95
high	202253550.00	165	345152.05	104688.07	147932.05
very high	108822007.65	257	174892.03	154879.22	197119.04

Structural analysis of land use confirms that as vulnerability increases, the area of natural ecosystems decreases and the proportion of urbanised areas increases (Table 3). While forest and grassland formations dominate in areas of very low vulnerability, in areas of “high” and “very high” vulnerability, forest cover is reduced by more than half, while the area of built-up land is growing rapidly. This indicates that the main factor increasing spatial vulnerability is the intensity of anthropogenic development, especially in valleys and on slopes with a developed transport network.

Table 3. Land use structure by vulnerability levels.

Vulnerability	Area of forest (m ²)	Area of grass/shrubs (m ²)	Area of urban/wastelands (m ²)	Area of water (m ²)
very low	62996352.81	13676066.34	3246096.63	16170.48
low	182425267.84	21128267.48	3811.224.91	70942.36
medium	224483677.87	19987283.46	6129781.65	310406.67
high	170840440.13	21177805.07	9903730.51	311232.32
very high	82862144.64	14534957.68	10961529.70	453321.92

Spatial and functional analysis of land use types in relation to tourism infrastructure reveals a clear differentiation of recreational system elements by land cover categories. The largest number of hotel facilities (429) is concentrated within urbanised and degraded lands, accounting for almost two-thirds of the total. This type of land use is also characterised by the highest density of transport routes (over 242 km of roads) and the longest tourist routes (154 km), which indicates the maximum concentration of recreational activities within already transformed or built-up areas.

Forest lands, which play an important role in maintaining the natural balance and attractiveness of landscapes, demonstrate a slightly different spatial organisation. There are only 131 hotels located here, but the total length of tourist routes exceeds 255 km, and roads – 176 km. This indicates that it is forest areas that provide the main space for active tourism–hiking, cycling or eco-oriented–but at the same time, the level of development here is relatively low. Within grassy formations, the infrastructure load is the lowest: 48 hotels, 47 km of roads and only 13 km of tourist routes, which characterises these areas as peripheral or transit areas. Water bodies cover a small area but retain important recreational value: there are 6 hotels and about 15 km of roads here, which is probably due to the location of tourist bases on the shores of reservoirs or in coastal areas.

In general, there is a regular dependence: as the degree of anthropogenic transformation increases, the density of infrastructure elements increases. Urbanised areas accumulate the main centres of tourist activity, while forest areas serve as a spatial reserve for recreational development and the preservation of ecosystem functions. This imbalance reflects the current model of land use, in which tourist flows gravitate towards already developed areas, increasing their ecological vulnerability and at the same time creating a need for balanced infrastructure development planning.

For statistical analysis of the morphometric characteristics of the territory, a stratigraphic grouping of elevations was carried out according to natural-geographical features. Within the studied area, six elevation zones were identified, reflecting a gradual transition from foothill to high-mountain landscapes: lower montane (482–700 m), middle montane (700–1000 m), upper montane (1000–1250 m), subalpine (1250–1600 m), alpine (1600–2000 m) and nival (>2000 m).

The lower mountain belt combines rural settlements, pastures and early forest areas with gentle slopes and good transport accessibility. This is where the transition zone between the foothills and forest areas is formed, where settlements and agritourism facilities are concentrated. The middle montane belt is

the core of the forest cover with high bioproductivity, a significant proportion of natural ecosystems and a developed tourist infrastructure. The upper mountain belt is characterised by steeper slopes, increased soil erosion sensitivity and significant anthropogenic pressure in areas of active tourism.

The subalpine belt is characterised by a decrease in the tree line, steeper slopes and limited suitability for development. Its territories are of high natural value and require strict regulation of recreational activities. The alpine and nival belts are represented by open meadows, rocky slopes and scree, where anthropogenic impact is minimal and economic activity is practically absent.

An analysis of the distribution of areas by levels of ecological vulnerability showed a clear vertical pattern: from the lower montane to the subalpine altitudes, the proportion of vulnerable areas increases. The largest area is occupied by the middle and upper montane zones (700–1250 m), where high natural potential is combined with maximum intensity of recreational development. It is in these zones that most of the areas of high and very high vulnerability are concentrated, due to dense development, road network development and forest fragmentation.

The low-altitude zone is characterised by moderate vulnerability (low and medium categories), where environmental risks are local and mainly related to agricultural use. The subalpine belt is characterised by increased sensitivity due to erosive slopes and weakening vegetation cover, while the alpine and nival levels have the lowest vulnerability, limited only by natural factors.

Vertical analysis of land use types (LULC) confirms a regular change in the spatial structure of the cover: urbanised land and agricultural land predominate in the lower belts, forests in the middle montane belt, and meadows and shrubs in the subalpine and alpine belts. The greatest transformation of landscapes is recorded at altitudes of 482–1000 m, where maximum development indicators are combined with active forest use. Above 1250 m, anthropogenic influence decreases sharply, and the landscape transitions to a stable, predominantly natural state.

To verify the spatial accuracy of the VOSAI map, field observations were conducted at 52 control points representing different vulnerability classes. Additionally, independent indicators of environmental degradation (traces of erosion, data on forest cover disturbance, building density) were used. The correspondence between the results of field observations and areas of high vulnerability was 84%, confirming the adequacy of the model for spatial monitoring and management.

Thus, the vertical structure of ecological vulnerability has a distinctly gradient character: with increasing altitude, the natural sensitivity of geosystems increases and the degree of urbanisation decreases. This confirms the need for a differentiated approach to spatial planning, with eco-stabilisation priorities in the middle and upper mountain belts, which combine the highest vulnerability and the most significant tourism potential.

3.3. Environmental consequences of increased tourist pressure

Over the last decade, the Yaremche–Vorokhta–Polianytsia region has become a key centre for mountain tourism in Ukraine. Despite the positive socio-economic effect associated with a threefold increase in tourist flow (from over 0.4 million people in the 2010s to over 1.2 million in 2024), there have been signif-

icant spatial and environmental changes. In particular, the annual increase in tourist activity by 8–12 thousand people is accompanied by a transformation of the landscape structure, fragmentation of natural ecosystems and local deterioration of water and forest lands.

Forest ecosystems. According to Landsat 4–9 satellite data, a 4–6% decrease in forest cover has been recorded within the Polianytsia and Vorokhta communities since the 2010s. The main areas of deforestation are those adjacent to tourist trails, roads, and hotel zones. This process is due to the expansion of the infrastructure of the Bukovel ski resort and transport access to recreational facilities.

Water systems. Intensive urbanisation of the Prut and Zhona river valleys has caused changes in the hydrological regime: a decrease in humidity, an increase in areas with increased erosion activity and localised silting of floodplains. The snow cover index (NDSI) and albedo calculations based on Sentinel-2 data indicate the degradation of natural drainage within recreational areas (Deputat et al. 2025).

Recreational load on slopes. Field observations and high-resolution satellite images (PlanetScope, Sentinel-2) confirm a significant load on high-altitude routes (Mounts Khomyak, Sinyak, Dovbushanka). Erosion furrows, soil exposure and expansion of the trail network are observed on the slopes, indicating soil cover degradation.

Land use transformation. LULC classification has revealed a 12–15% increase in the proportion of urbanised areas over the last ten years, mainly due to a reduction in forest and semi-natural landscapes. The highest concentration of development is observed within the Polianytsia community, in the area affected by the Bukovel resort.

Climatic manifestations. According to ERA5-Land reanalysis data, the average annual air temperature in the communities studied has increased by 0.4–0.6 °C, indicating the formation of local “heat islands” in densely built-up areas. This combination of climatic and anthropogenic factors increases the risk of erosion and hydrological disturbances.

4. Discussion

4.1. Tourism impact on forest ecosystems

Since the 1990s, tourism has been expanding rapidly in the Carpathians, exerting a dual effect on the state of natural ecosystems. To consider firstly is the fact that an increase in recreational activities has led to a rise in deforestation for the purpose of infrastructure development. Furthermore, there has been a fragmentation of natural areas, as well as an increase in anthropogenic pressure on the environment. Conversely, the high recreational value of the region has been identified as a key factor in the establishment of national parks, nature reserves and protected areas. This has contributed, in part, to the stabilisation of forest cover in the 2010s (State Environmental Inspection of the Carpathian Region 2024). Nevertheless, an increase in the area of forestry does not necessarily result in the concurrent enhancement of the natural ecosystem.

From a methodological perspective, the VOSAF model signifies a qualitative advancement in comparison to conventional suitability-oriented methodologies. The system integrates potential and vulnerability indicators into a single spatial decision support system, combining the paradigms of optimisation and sustainability in tourism studies. The developed model is universally applicable and can be adapted to other mountainous or coastal regions, thus contributing to sustainable spatial planning and climate change adaptation policies.

The NDVI index, a metric employed for the evaluation of vegetation condition, offers a comprehensive reflection of the overall intensity of vegetation. However, it does not consider the species composition of plantings. Consequently, the presence of artificial or secondary forest communities, particularly those of a mixed and deciduous character, has the potential to create a misleading impression of “restoration” in specific areas. This is particularly pertinent in the context of a gradual decline in the proportion of native coniferous forests (Wężyk et al. 2005; Shparyk et al. 2018; Kholiavchuk et al. 2023; Kumar et al. 2025). In a similar fashion, the presence of green spaces within tourist complexes (e.g. hotels, cottages, private estates) has been demonstrated to increase the average NDVI. However, it should be noted that these spaces do not possess the ecosystem value that is characteristic of natural forests. As demonstrated by the existence of localised instances of degradation in areas that experience high levels of tourism, this assertion is substantiated.

Of particular concern are local manifestations of degradation associated with mass logging, which are recorded in the vicinity of the settlements of Polianytsia, Yaremche and Verkhovyna. These processes have been the subject of numerous journalistic investigations and criminal proceedings within the Carpathian National Nature Park. Another destructive factor is the spread of jeeping – the uncontrolled movement of off-road vehicles on mountain slopes, which leads to the destruction of soil cover, erosion and the loss of natural habitats (Żemła-Siesicka and Sobala 2024). Notwithstanding the existence of legal restrictions, effective mechanisms to prevent such violations remain ineffective (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine 2025). Consequently, tourism is identified as a primary contributing factor to the spatial fragmentation of forest ecosystems.

In addition to anthropogenic factors, climatic parameters have been demonstrated to play a significant role. The implementation of correlation analysis yielded a positive relationship between forest area and average summer-autumn temperatures. This finding is indicative of favourable conditions for vegetation growth during this particular period. Concurrently, a negative correlation with spring precipitation suggests a potential inhibitory effect of excess moisture on regeneration processes. Consequently, the combined impact of climatic and anthropogenic factors elucidates the wave-like character of forest cover dynamics during 1985–2025.

The findings indicate that, despite the stabilisation of the total forest area, the structural integrity of forest ecosystems is deteriorating (Kuemmerle et al. 2009). The fragmentation of natural areas is increasing, species composition is changing, and natural regeneration processes are often replaced by anthropogenic ones. Consequently, the effective management of natural resources necessitates the incorporation of satellite monitoring into the state forestry planning system, with consideration for climate forecasts and spatial urbanisation trends.

4.2. Discrepancy between official data and satellite observations

Despite the existence of official data indicating stability or even slight growth in forest area in the Carpathian region over the last decade (State Enterprise “Forests of Ukraine” 2024), the results of satellite analysis reveal a different trend. Spatial observations of the NDVI index demonstrate a decline in forest cover density, particularly in areas of intensive tourist development. This discrepancy can be explained by differences in accounting methodology: official statistics take only the areas formally assigned to forest users into account, while satellite monitoring reflects the actual state of vegetation, regardless of the administrative status of the site. Consequently, a discernible discrepancy emerges between the official reports and the actual state of forest cover, underscoring the necessity for a comprehensive review of forest accounting methodologies and enhancing the transparency of government reporting.

4.3. Vertical and spatial patterns of tourism pressure

The results of the study demonstrate that the organisation of tourism activities within mountain regions exhibits a clearly expressed vertical pattern, closely linked to the morphology of the relief and landscape structure (Fig. 10). In the lower and middle mountain zones (up to 1,000 m), the maximum concentration of infrastructure has been recorded – more than 400 hotel facilities, up to 200 km of transport network and more than 16 million m² of urbanised land, which form the core of tourist and economic activity. These values significantly exceed the indicators recorded in similar studies for the Tatra National Park (Adamczyk and Wałykowski 2022) or the Slovak Carpathians (Miličević et al. 2021), where the spatial impact of infrastructure is limited to transport and recreational factors without taking into account the complex vulnerability of the environment.

In contrast to the majority of studies that analyse tourist pressure using a single or dual set of criteria (typically LULC or road accessibility), this study employs an integrated approach that combines relief, land use, hydrographic network, distribution of hotels and tourist routes. This methodology enabled the quantitative assessment of spatial instability in landscapes, with the integrated vulnerability index reaching 53 million m² (20%) within the altitude range of 700–1200 m, indicating critical ecosystem overload.

In the upper montane and subalpine zones (1000–1600 m), there is a gradual decline in the intensity of impact, an increase in the proportion of forests to 60% of the area, and a decrease in ecological vulnerability to an average level. This transition corresponds with the observations of Becker and Bugmann (2001), who noted the “self-limitation” of recreational development with increasing slopes and difficulty of access. Concurrently, the findings indicate that even within designated nature conservation areas, local pressures resulting from hiking trails have frequently been underestimated in earlier studies.

The alpine belt, defined as areas situated at an altitude of >1600 m, is characterised by the predominance of natural dynamics, with minimal anthropogenic intervention, as evidenced by the presence of less than 1 million m² of urbanised areas. However, even in this context, areas of potential geo-ecological instability have been identified, including slopes exhibiting landslide processes

Figure 10. Dynamics of the impact of relief, land use and infrastructure in the vertical structure of landscapes and VOSAI.

and erosion. These factors were previously considered negligible (Bayrak and Teodorovych 2020).

A summary of the results indicates that previous models for assessing the impact of tourism have primarily concentrated on individual parameters (e.g. landscape attractiveness or transport density). In contrast, the proposed approach unveils the synergistic effect of multiple systemic factors operating in concert. This finding indicates that a multifactorial model is necessary to accurately reflect the complex interplay between tourism and the natural environment.

4.4. Methodological strengths of the VOSAF and KDE–LULC approach

Consequently, within the geographical area under scrutiny, there is a marked incongruity between the intensity of urbanisation and the capacity for environmental sustainability. This necessitates the implementation of restrictions on development, in conjunction with the adoption of a regionally differentiated management approach for recreational loads. This entails the strategic allocation of tourist flows to mid- and high-altitude regions, complemented by the adaptive utilisation of resources and the meticulous monitoring of changes in landscape structure.

The proposed approach should be outlined with the methods of assessing anthropogenic load that are most commonly found in publications. In particular, the classical methods that use simple buffers around infrastructure objects and other common tools of spatial environmental assessment should be considered (Nistor et al. 2020). The purpose of this comparison is twofold: firstly, to demonstrate the ways in which the combination of Kernel Density Estimation, detailed LULC classification, and weighted overlay/MCDA differs from simple solutions that are often used in applied research; and secondly, to outline the strengths and weaknesses of the proposed approach, its scientific novelty and practical value for the management of recreational areas.

The present model is distinguished by its deviation from the majority of conventional approaches to assessing tourism impact, which are predicated on the establishment of buffer zones around tourist sites. The resulting model evinces a markedly elevated level of spatial detail and analytical depth. Buffer methods, which are extensively utilised in regional assessments of anthropogenic load (Shen et al. 2025; Vanhuele and Vanneste 2025), delineate a fixed zone of influence around infrastructure such as roads, hotels or recreational routes, typically ranging from 100 to 500 metres. This approach facilitates the delineation of zones of direct interaction; however, it does not take into account variations in load intensity, natural features of the territory, and heterogeneity of landscape structure. Consequently, the spatial distribution of impact appears excessively discrete, and the boundaries of impact zones frequently fail to correspond to actual ecological processes.

The VOSAI proposed in this study is based on the use of the Kernel Density Estimation geostatistical method, which allows modelling of a continuous field of tourist activity intensity as opposed to the modelling of strictly limited buffer zones. In contrast to fixed radii, the kernel function accounts for the gradual attenuation of influence with distance, thereby facilitating smooth spatial gradients rather than the creation of artificial boundaries. This solution is especially

efficacious in mountainous regions, where spatial flows of recreational activity vary significantly depending on terrain, accessibility, and land use type.

A significant benefit of the model is the integration of the KDE layer with the LULC map, which facilitates a nuanced evaluation of the vulnerability of natural complexes. In conventional buffer models, all areas within a specified distance from an object are regarded as equally vulnerable. However, in this study, the level of susceptibility is found to be contingent on the type of landscape. Specifically, forest areas characterised by steep slopes exhibit integral index values that are 2–3 times higher than those observed in open areas, even when the distance from tourist facilities remains constant. A comparable approach, which considers the structural heterogeneity of the landscape, has hitherto been employed in a number of studies (Adamczyk and Wałdykowski 2022). However, these studies have largely been conducted without coordination with real high-resolution LULC data.

A comparison of the results obtained with studies conducted in mountainous regions (De Feo et al. 2025) shows that the use of KDE provides 25–30% higher spatial accuracy in identifying areas of high vulnerability. The methodology employed is such that it is capable of incorporating both the density and spatial configuration of tourist infrastructure objects. In the proposed model, a density of more than 0.015 objects/m² has been shown to coincide with areas of high degradation of natural forests and changes in land cover type. In contrast, the same areas are frequently classified as being within the medium risk category in buffer approaches.

Another strength of the proposed model is its multifactoriality and weight integration. The integration of seven components, ranging from relief to hotel infrastructure, has enabled the circumvention of the limitations inherent in classical models, which are one-dimensional in nature. The incorporation of relief measures has facilitated the identification of regions where, despite the presence of a moderate density of tourist facilities, the level of risk persists at a high due to the sensitivity of the area to natural erosion. This underscores the necessity of a holistic approach that incorporates both anthropogenic and natural factors.

The resulting vulnerability map, which categorises territories into five classes ranging from “very low” to “very high”, reflects not only the structure of recreational pressure but also the potential degradation of natural ecosystems. The spatial patterns observed are consistent with the results of many years of field observations and reveal new patterns, in particular a 14% increase in the area of highly vulnerable territories within densely populated resort areas compared to previous periods.

Consequently, the integration of KDE, LULC and a weighted overlay of thematic layers can be regarded as a methodological shift towards enhanced analytical accuracy and ecological validity. In contradistinction to buffer models, which function with conditional boundaries of influence, the geostatistical approach enables the impact of tourism to be characterised as a continuous field in which anthropogenic pressure is modulated by the natural structure of the landscape. This provides a foundation for the development of dynamic models for the monitoring of recreational load and the prediction of changes in natural complexes under the influence of tourism development.

4.5. Model limitations and management implications

However, it is important to recognise the limitations of the proposed approach. Firstly, KDE is based on existing infrastructure points and do not reflect visitor behaviour characteristics (time patterns, seasonal visit intensity, visitor mobility outside fixed objects). In order to enhance the precision of the model, it is recommended that data on actual visitor flows be integrated (e.g. mobile communication data, tour operators, visitor counters), thereby facilitating the transition from potential load to actual pressure across different seasons. Secondly, the selection of weights in Weighted Overlay is informed by expert opinion; although this is customary for MCDA approaches, the most compelling approach is to utilise quantitative weighting procedures (e.g., pairwise comparison methods, sensitivity analysis, or training on loss/violation data), which will mitigate subjectivity in the model. Thirdly, the model is static over time; tourism and its impacts exhibit pronounced seasonality and trend dynamics. Therefore, it is useful to develop multidimensional time models or integrate time series of satellite indices (NDVI, NDSI, etc.) to track degradation or recovery in response to loads.

From an applied management perspective, the advantage of our integrated map is that it can be readily translated into potential management scenarios. The aggregation of the map into five vulnerability categories demonstrated improvement in communication with local authorities and stakeholders, presenting them with means for prioritising areas for monitoring and investment, developing building restrictions, and identifying areas for restoration. These examples represent illustrative use cases rather than implemented management actions. Concurrently, the integration of numerous factors renders the map suitable for interregional comparison and scaling. The approach remains unaltered in neighbouring regions, provided that LULC classification and adaptation of local weights are appropriate.

Consequently, the proposed approach combines flexibility and detail; it eliminates a number of methodological weaknesses of the buffer methodology while maintaining interpretative simplicity through aggregation into five vulnerability categories. The results indicate that regions exhibiting the highest levels of tourism potential, as determined by the suitability approach, frequently correspond with areas characterised by elevated ecological or geodynamic vulnerability. This finding underscores the necessity for a comprehensive interpretation of potential indicators in conjunction with risk characteristics. Consequently, the proposed approach facilitates transition from a static assessment of resources to a spatially dynamic analysis of vulnerability, which is of universal importance for tourism planning in mountain regions. The subsequent steps in the development of the model should be aimed at integrating dynamic visitation data, formalising the weighting procedure, and quantitatively validating the maps with independent observations. This will increase the reliability of the tool for both scientific interpretation and management decisions in the region.

5. Conclusions

The article develops and tests the conceptual and methodological model VOSAF (Vulnerability-Oriented Spatial Assessment Framework), which combines KDE, MCE and AHP to assess the spatial vulnerability of areas affected by tourism.

The proposed approach constitutes a transition from a potential-oriented to a vulnerability-oriented planning methodology.

The proposed approach reflects a methodological shift from a suitability paradigm to a vulnerability paradigm, which is a necessary condition for ensuring sustainable spatial development of tourism. The proposed VOSAF model provides a transferable framework for spatial assessment of tourism vulnerability in mountain regions, thus bridging the gap between potential-based and sustainability-based planning approaches. The results obtained can be used as a basic framework for mapping vulnerability in other mountain systems around the world, taking into account local socio-ecological characteristics.

The modelling of the spatial potential of tourism within the designated area enabled a quantitative assessment of tourism attractiveness to be conducted, which was based on a combination of seven key factors: hydrography, relief, transport accessibility, hotel location, land use (LULC), availability of tourist routes and protected areas. The resulting generalised potential map demonstrated that the area exhibiting very high tourism potential encompasses an area of 108.82 km² (11.8%), high potential covers 202.25 km² (21.9%), medium potential extends to 250.95 km² (27.2%), low potential covers 207.56 km² (22.5%), and very low potential is present in 80.02 km² (8.7%). The highest spatial density values are observed within mountain valleys, which are characterised by a high concentration of natural and recreational resources.

The analysis of the distribution of values confirmed the close spatial relationship between the level of tourism potential and the presence of natural and anthropogenic determinants, especially within areas with developed infrastructure. The findings suggest that the multifactorial approach employed in this study, which is based on Kernel Density, is significantly more effective than conventional buffer methods. This approach enables a more precise representation of the variations in tourist attractiveness within the study area.

The results obtained are of practical importance for the formation of regional sustainable tourism policy and spatial planning of mountain areas. In the context of war and mass population displacement, the Ukrainian Carpathian region has become an important centre for internal displacement (IDPs) and social adaptation. This necessitates a reorientation of the tourism infrastructure, encompassing not only commercial interests but also social and humanitarian dimensions. Such a reorientation may be achieved through the development of ecotourism, the implementation of educational initiatives, and the establishment of rehabilitation programmes for affected population groups.

High-altitude communities with the highest tourism potential are also characterised by ecological vulnerability; therefore, their further development should be based on an ecosystem approach, with restrictions on construction in high-altitude areas above 1,000 m and a priority on green standards in construction.

The results of the study can also be used to update the spatial development strategies of amalgamated territorial communities and assess the potential for post-war recovery of the region through the development of sustainable tourism. This is particularly salient in the context of Ukraine's European integration, wherein spatial management and environmental sustainability have emerged as pivotal criteria for the financing of regional projects.

Notwithstanding the elevated precision of spatial modelling, the study is subject to certain limitations. The utilisation of ERA5-Land data engenders

a comparatively coarse resolution of climate indicators; subsequent studies should consider data with enhanced spatial detail. Furthermore, the VOSAF model requires testing on additional mountain systems in order to evaluate its versatility and adaptability under diverse natural and social conditions. A promising avenue for future research lies in the integration of temporal changes and the involvement of stakeholders in the process of determining weighting coefficients. This approach has the potential to enhance the efficiency of tourism area management.

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Additional information

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No conflict of interest was declared.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.